

INDIGENOUS MICROAGGRESSION SCALE FOR PAKISTAN:
DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION.

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Abstract

Background: Microaggressions are subtle, often unintentional forms of discrimination that communicate hostility, exclusion, or invalidation toward marginalized groups. Despite growing international literature on microaggressions, there is a paucity of culturally grounded assessment tools for use in Pakistan.

Objectives: The present study aimed to develop and validate the Forman Microaggression Scale (FMS), an indigenous measure designed to capture contextually relevant microaggressive experiences among Pakistani adults.

Method: Using a multistage scale development process, items were generated through literature review, expert consultation, and qualitative inputs. The preliminary pool was administered to a diverse sample of young adults (N=433) to establish preliminary psychometric features of the newly developed measure.

Result: Statistical analyses revealed a stable multidimensional structure reflecting interpersonal, institutional, and identity-based microaggressions. The final scale demonstrated strong internal consistency and satisfactory evidence of construct validity. Findings highlight the importance of culturally sensitive measurement of microaggressions in non-Western contexts.

Conclusion: The Forman Microaggression Scale provides researchers and practitioners in Pakistan with a psychometrically sound tool for assessing subtle discrimination and its psychological impact, with implications for research, clinical practice, and policy.

INTRODUCTION

Microaggressions refer to brief and commonplace verbal, behavioral, or environmental indignities that convey negative or derogatory messages toward individuals based on their group membership (Nadal, 2011; Sue et al., 2007). Originally conceptualized within the context of racial discrimination, the concept has since expanded to include gender, religion, ethnicity, social class, disability, and other marginalized identities (Lilienfeld, 2017). Unlike overt discrimination, microaggressions are often ambiguous and normalized, making them difficult to identify and

address, yet their cumulative psychological impact can be profound (Sue & Spanierman, 2020).

The concept of microaggression has evolved over several decades, beginning with subtle, covert, and often unintentional backhanded comments directed at women these behaviors are typically short-lived, unrecognized by perpetrators, and occur in contexts where individuals are perceived as different (Rowe, 2008; Torino et al., 2019). Over time, the use of the term expanded to encompass the unintentional and unintended demeaning of various socially marginalized groups, including those marginalized

on the basis of gender, disability, health status, socioeconomic background, race, and sexual orientation (Paludi & Denmark, 2011). Building on this broader understanding, Sue (2010) defined microaggressions as brief and commonplace verbal, behavioral, or environmental indignities whether intentional or unintentional that convey hostile, disparaging, or negative messages toward individuals or groups based on aspects of their identity such as race, religion, disability, health status, or sexual orientation (Pérez Huber & Solorzano, 2015; Williams, 2020). Micro aggressive behaviors are broadly categorized in four primary forms namely microinsults, microinvalidations, microassaults and environmental microaggressions (Sue et al., 2007). These different forms are basically the manifestation of microaggression in everyday life as the way of expression including verbal, gestural or behavioral (Torres et al., 2019).

Microinsults are humiliations of subtle form that communicate insensitivity and rudeness towards social identities of individuals (Tran & Lee, 2014). Micro-invalidations subtly negates and exclude the psychological feelings, thoughts, or the experiential realities of an individual or group especially the ones carrying the element of marginalization (Brown-Johnson et al., 2020). Micro-assaults surface as specific form of microaggression characterized by their overt discriminatory actions or comments aimed at individuals or groups which are associated with any marginalizing aspect (Kocalan, 2023, McCallaghan & Steyn, 2024). Environmental microaggressions involves unintentional, discriminatory behaviors, gestures or comments that occur within a specific social setting (Westover, 2025). Microaggressive behaviors can be part of everyday communication of good-intentioned individuals (Hudson & Hunter, 2020; Riel, 2019).

In Western contexts, research has consistently linked experiences of microaggressions with adverse mental health outcomes, including depression, anxiety, stress, and reduced well-being (Anderson et al., 2020; Spanierman et al., 2021; Williams et al., 2021). Repeated exposure to subtle invalidation and exclusion can erode self-esteem and foster chronic psychological distress (Lilienfeld, 2017; Mouzon et al., 2017). Consequently, accurate assessment of

microaggressions is essential for understanding their prevalence and impact (Michaels et al., 2018).

Despite Pakistan's rich cultural, ethnic, linguistic, and religious diversity, empirical research on microaggressions remains extremely limited. Pakistani society is characterized by complex social hierarchies shaped by gender norms, sectarian identities, ethnic differences, socioeconomic status, and language. These sociocultural dynamics create fertile ground for microaggressive interactions that may differ substantially from those documented in Western societies. However, most existing microaggression scales have been developed in Western contexts and may fail to capture culturally specific forms of subtle discrimination prevalent in Pakistan.

The absence of an indigenous, psychometrically sound instrument represents a significant gap in Pakistani psychological research. Without culturally valid measures, researchers risk underestimating or mischaracterizing the lived experiences of marginalized individuals. Therefore, the present study aimed to develop and validate the Forman Microaggression Scale (FMS), a culturally grounded measure designed specifically for use in Pakistan.

Methodology

The study employed an instrument development and validation design, following established psychometric guidelines. DeVellis' (2017) classical model of scale development was employed for designing the methodology of the present study. The process consisted of item generation, expert review, pilot testing, and large-scale validation steps.

Participants

The refined scale was administered to a sample of 433 adult participants recruited from various universities and community settings through purposes sampling technique. Participants represented diverse backgrounds in terms of gender, socioeconomic status, and educational level. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents.

Procedure

A multiphase procedure of scale construction was adopted to develop the scale. In phase 1, items were

generated through an indepth review of literature and focus group discussions. The aim of phase-1 was to identify culturally specific microaggressive experiences related to gender, religion, ethnicity, language, and socioeconomic status indigenous to Pakistani culture. Whereas in phase 2, item analysis was carried out in three steps, that is, establishment of content validity, construct validity and reliability. Data were collected using a self-report questionnaire format. Participants were instructed to rate the frequency with which they experienced each microaggressive behavior on a Likert-type scale. Ethical approval was obtained prior to data collection, and confidentiality was ensured.

Data was processed through Statistical Package for Social Scinces (SPSS) and main statistical procedures included correlation analyses, factor analysis and reliability analyses. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was conducted to examine the construct validity. Internal consistency (reliability) was assessed using Cronbach’s alpha coefficients. Evidence of content validity and construct validity was further evaluated through correlations and factor interpretability.

Results

Women made the majority of the sample (73 %), the educational level of majority of participants was bachelors (67 %) with high school certificate as the minimum education (1 %) and postgraduate degree as the highest educational qualification (25 %). The mean age of the sample was 23.02 (SD=8.93). Single participants (70 %) dominated the sample and no participant reported any significant history of

psychological illness or physical disability. Participants were mostly following the religion Islam (90 %) and participants following Hinduism were lowest in number (1%). Most of the sample consisted of students who lived in urban areas, nuclear household and had their origin as Punjabi. Large amount of sample practiced heterosexual sexual orientation.

The initial item pool of 117 was thoroughly assessed through the structured procedure of content validity, from which 117 items in total received the rating of .83 which was way above the minimum cutoff criteria contingent to number of raters involved according to the guidelines provided by Polit and Beck (2006). Therefore, 35 items were eliminated for having content validity ratings lower than the cutoff point.

Construct validity of the scale was established through exploratory factor analysis. Basic descriptive procedures and review of bivariate scatter plots were employed to identify any outliers in the dataset (Garson, 2022). Correlation matrices were used to assess the suitability of dataset for factor analysis as depicted by majority of the correlations falling at 0.30 and above (Field, 2009). Principal Component Analysis of Exploratory Factor Analysis with orthogonal rotation method (varimax) was selected based on the relatedness of items from the correlation matrix. Additionally, 0.40 was chosen as the cut-off value for item selection. Finally, a four factor structure was finally selected based on factor loadings, Eigen values, scree plot and total variance explained.

Table 1 Eigen Values and Variance Explained by Factors of Microaggression Scale

Factors	Eigen Values	% of Variance	Cumulative Percentage
1- CAI	15.90	38.78	38.78
2- IDD	2.92	7.13	45.99
3- IBS	1.78	4.32	50.23
4- SCS	1.68	4.09	54.32

Note. CAI= Conditional Acceptance of Identity, IDD= Interpersonal Disrespect and Dismissal, IBS= Identity-Based Stereotyping, SCS= Status and Competence Stereotyping.

The table indicated that the four factors together explained 54 percent of the total variance which falls

above the minimum acceptable level of variance i.e. 50 percent which is deemed good factor structure.

Figure 1. Scree-Plot of Factors of Microaggression Scale

Scree-plot highlights the suitability of a four-factor solution for this newly developed scale. Details of the factors and items are mentioned below.

Factor 1- Conditional Acceptance of Identity (CAI). Items loaded on the first factor depicted a common theme of people’s discomfort, devaluation and superficial tolerance towards a person’s identity or background, rather than full respect and inclusion for them. Therefore, it was decided to name the factor as “Conditional Acceptance of Identity”.

Factor 2- Interpersonal Disrespect and Dismissal (IDD). Items loaded on second factor revolve around objectification, invalidation and discomfort caused by words and behaviors of people which are often

disguised as compliments, jokes and even well-meaning responses. Therefore, the factor was named “Interpersonal Disrespect and Dismissal”.

Factor 3- Identity-Based Stereotyping (IBS). Items are based on prejudice, blatant stereotyping and discriminatory treatment loaded which led to assumptions about morality, inferiority and criminality. Therefore, these themes led to name of “Identity-Based Stereotyping”.

Factor 4- Status and Competence Stereotyping (SCS). Assumptions of inferiority, status and competence emerged as the theme for this factor. Therefore, it was named as “Status and Competence Stereotyping”.

Table 2 Inter Scale Correlation of Forman Microaggression Scale

Factors	CAI	IDD	IBS	SCS
CAI	—			
IDD	.675**	—		
IBS	.713**	.524**	—	
SCS	.588**	.554**	.602**	—
Full Scale	.945**	.842**	.794**	.715**

Note. **Correlation is significant at the .01 level (2-tailed). CAI= Conditional Acceptance of Identity, IDD= Interpersonal Disrespect and Dismissal, IBS= Identity-Based Stereotyping, SCS= Status and Competence Stereotyping.

Inter-scale correlations among the factors of the Forman Microaggression Scale indicated that all four factors were significantly and positively correlated

with one another ($p < .01$). Correlation coefficients ranged from moderate to high, indicating related yet distinct dimensions of microaggression scale.

Specifically, CAI demonstrated strong positive associations with IBS ($p < .01$) and IDD ($p < .01$), suggesting that conditional acceptance of identity is closely linked with experiences of stereotyping and interpersonal invalidation. Moderate correlations were also observed between IDD and IBS ($p < .01$), as well as between SCS and the other factors ($p < .01$).

Importantly, all four factors showed very strong correlations with the full scale score (ranging from $r = .72$ to $.95$, $p < .01$), providing robust evidence that each factor meaningfully contributes to the overall construct of microaggression. These findings support the presence of a common underlying latent trait while retaining meaningful multidimensionality.

Table 3 Mean, Standard Deviation and Range for Factor Scores of Forman Microaggression Scale

Variables	Mean	SD	Range
CAI	52.56	23.58	19-122
IDD	37.80	14.73	11-75
IBS	17.87	7.82	7-40
SCS	16.08	6.72	5-35
Full Scale	121.04	44.70	41-242

Note. CAI= Conditional Acceptance of Identity, IDD= Interpersonal Disrespect and Dismissal, IBS= Identity-Based Stereotyping, SCS= Status and Competence Stereotyping.

Table 3 depicts that CAI yielded the highest mean score ($M = 52.56$), followed by IDD ($M = 37.80$), IBS ($M = 17.87$) and SCS ($M = 16.08$). The full-scale mean was 121.04 ($SD = 44.70$), with scores spanning a wide range (41-242), indicating substantial variability in participants' experiences of microaggressions. The broad ranges and relatively large standard deviations across factors suggest that

experiences of microaggression vary considerably among individuals, supporting the sensitivity of the scale in capturing differential exposure to subtle discriminatory behaviors.

To assess the internal consistency of the Forman Microaggression Scale, Cronbach's alpha was measured to ensure that all items, the results are as follows;

Table 4 Internal Consistency of Forman Microaggression Scale

Factors	Number of Items	α
CAI	19	.95
IDD	11	.90
IBS	7	.84
SCS	5	.82
Full Scale	42	.96

Internal consistency estimates for the Forman Microaggression Scale and its subscales are reported in Table 4. Cronbach's alpha coefficients indicated excellent reliability for the full scale ($\alpha = .96$). Subscale reliabilities were also strong, with $\alpha = .95$ for CAI, $\alpha = .90$ for IDD, $\alpha = .84$ for IBS, and $\alpha = .82$ for SCS. All reliability coefficients exceeded the recommended minimum threshold of .80, demonstrating that the items within each factor consistently measure the same underlying construct.

The exceptionally high internal consistency of the full scale further supports the overall reliability of the FMS and aligns with psychometric standards for scale development (Groth-Marnat, 2003).

Discussion

The present study sought to address a critical gap in Pakistani psychological research by developing an indigenous measure of microaggressions. The findings provide strong preliminary support for the

reliability and validity of the Forman Microaggression Scale. The multidimensional structure reflects the complex ways in which microaggressions manifest in Pakistani social contexts, encompassing interpersonal interactions, institutional practices, and identity-related invalidation.

A rather strict cut off point of 0.40 loadings was selected to retain items which resulted in four factor structure reducing items to only 41. Keeping in mind the data consideration (Clark & Watson, 2019; Coner, 2009), Principal Component Analysis with varimax rotation were selected based on data consideration and test construction guidelines in literature Exploratory (Hofmann & Kashdan, 2010; Preacher & MacCallum, 2003; Watson & Thompson, 2006).

The appropriateness of the data for adequate factoring is indicated by the Kaiser Myer Olkin (KMO) estimate for sampling appropriateness with .97 value falling in the excellent range for factor analysis (Field, 2009). High significance for sample and data adequacy were also exhibited by significant value of Bartlette Test of Sphericity ($p < .001$) (Field, 2009). Additionally, Nadal et al. (2011) employed Varimax rotation in the development of the Racial and Ethnic Microaggressions Scale (REMS), justifying its use based on low inter-factor correlations of the factors generated in a previous scale of Microaggression. This provides precedent for using Varimax in the current study Microaggression scale development. Four factor solution was deemed acceptable for this newly developed scale after trying different factor solutions. Eigen values, Catell's Scree Plot criteria and explained total variances showed support for this final solution (Costello & Osborne, 2005; Watson et al., 2005). A rather strict criterion of item loading was adopted by choosing 0.40 as the cut off value as experts consider that significant for screening tools having a sample of at least 100 participants (Carpenter, 2018; Kline, 2013).

Exploratory factor analysis supported a multidimensional structure of the Forman Microaggression Scale. Items clustered into distinct factors reflecting interpersonal microaggressions, institutional microaggressions, and identity-based invalidation. Factor loadings were satisfactory, and no substantial cross-loadings were observed,

indicating a clear and interpretable factor solution (Byrne, 2005; Yong & Pearce, 2013).

The final version of the scale demonstrated strong internal consistency, with Cronbach's alpha coefficients exceeding acceptable thresholds for psychological measurement. Item-total correlations further supported the homogeneity of the scale.

Preliminary evidence of construct validity was established through theoretically consistent patterns of associations among items and subscales. The factor structure aligned well with existing theoretical models of microaggressions while incorporating culturally specific dimensions relevant to Pakistani society.

The emergence of culturally specific factors underscores the limitations of relying solely on Western-developed instruments. Certain forms of subtle discrimination identified in this study, particularly those related to language, sectarian identity, and gender norms, may be underrepresented in existing scales. This highlights the importance of culturally grounded assessment tools for accurately capturing lived experiences.

From a theoretical perspective, the findings support the universality of microaggressions as a social phenomenon while emphasizing the need for contextual sensitivity. The Forman Microaggression Scale bridges global theoretical frameworks with local sociocultural realities.

Implications - The availability of a validated microaggression scale has important implications for research, clinical practice, and policy in Pakistan. Researchers can use the FMS to examine the prevalence and psychological impact of microaggressions across different populations. Clinicians may find the scale useful for assessing clients' experiences of subtle discrimination that contribute to psychological distress. At the policy level, the scale can inform institutional interventions aimed at promoting inclusion and equity.

Limitations and Future Directions - While the findings are promising, the study has limitations. The sample was primarily urban and educated, which may limit generalizability. Future research should validate the scale across diverse regions and populations. Confirmatory factor analysis is also recommended to further establish the scale's psychometric robustness.

Conclusion

The Forman Microaggression Scale represents a significant step toward culturally sensitive assessment of subtle discriminations in Pakistan. By providing a reliable and valid tool grounded in local sociocultural realities, the present study contributes to advancing research on microaggressions and their psychological consequences in non-Western contexts.

REFERENCE:

- Anderson, A. J., Sánchez, B., Reyna, C., & Rasgado-Flores, H. (2020). "It Just Weighs in the Back of your Mind": Microaggressions in Science. *Journal of Women and Minorities in Science and Engineering*, 26(1).
- Brown-Johnson, C., Shankar, M., Taylor, N. K., Safaainili, N., Shaw, J. G., Winget, M., & Mahoney, M. (2020). "Racial Bias... I'm Not Sure if It Has Affected My Practice": a Qualitative Exploration of Racial Bias in Team-Based Primary Care. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 35(11), 3395-3397.
- Byrne, B. M. (2005). Factor analytic models: Viewing the structure of an assessment instrument from three perspectives. *Journal of personality assessment*, 85(1), 17-32.
- Carpenter, S. (2018). Ten steps in scale development and reporting: A guide for researchers. *Communication methods and measures*, 12(1), 25-44.
- Clark, L. A., & Watson, D. (2019). Constructing validity: New developments in creating objective measuring instruments. *Psychological assessment*, 31(12), 1412.
- Corner, S. (2009). Choosing the right type of rotation in PCA and EFA. *JALT testing & evaluation SIG newsletter*, 13(3), 20-25.
- Costello, A. B., & Osborne, J. (2005). Best practices in exploratory factor analysis: Four recommendations for getting the most from your analysis. *Practical assessment, research, and evaluation*, 10(1).
- Field, A. (2009). *Spss. Discovering statistics using SPSS. 2nd ed. Porto Alegre, RS: Artmed.*
- Garson, G. D. (2022). *Factor analysis and dimension reduction in R: a social Scientist's toolkit.* Routledge.
- Groth-Marnat, G. (2009). *Handbook of psychological assessment.* John Wiley & Sons.
- Hofmann, S. G., & Kashdan, T. B. (2010). The affective style questionnaire: development and psychometric properties. *Journal of psychopathology and behavioral assessment*, 32(2), 255-263.
- Kline, R. (2013). Exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis. In *Applied quantitative analysis in education and the social sciences* (pp. 171-207). Routledge.
- Kocalan, E. B. (2023). Microaggression and Japanese Muslim Women. *Hitit İlahiyat Dergisi*, 919-937.
- Lilienfeld, S. O. (2017). Microaggressions: Strong claims, inadequate evidence. *Perspectives on psychological science*, 12(1), 138-169.
- McCallaghan, S., & Steyn, R. (2024). Operationalizing microaggressions: Definitions, conceptualization and typologies. *Journal of Social Science Studies*, 11(1), 195-195.
- Michaels, T. I., Gallagher, N., Crawford, M., Kanter, J. W., & Williams, M. T. (2018). Racial differences in the appraisal of microaggressions through cultural consensus modeling. *The Behavior Therapist*, 41(7), 314-321.
- Mouzon, D. M., Taylor, R. J., Keith, V. M., Nicklett, E. J., & Chatters, L. M. (2017). Discrimination and psychiatric disorders among older African Americans. *International journal of geriatric psychiatry*, 32(2), 175-182.
- Nadal, K. L. (2011). The Racial and Ethnic Microaggressions Scale (REMS): construction, reliability, and validity. *Journal of counseling psychology*, 58(4), 470.
- Nadal, K. L., Issa, M. A., Leon, J., Meterko, V., Wideman, M., & Wong, Y. (2011). Sexual orientation microaggressions: "Death by a thousand cuts" for lesbian, gay, and bisexual youth. *Journal of LGBT youth*, 8(3), 234-259.
- Paludi, M. A., & Denmark, F. L. (2011). Many phantoms and obstacles... looming in her way": Women faculty in academe. *Women as leaders in education. Succeeding despite inequity, discrimination, and other challenges*, 45-78.

- Pérez Huber, L., & Solorzano, D. G. (2015). Racial microaggressions as a tool for critical race research. *Race Ethnicity and Education*, 18(3), 297-320.
- Preacher, K. J., & MacCallum, R. C. (2003). Repairing Tom Swift's electric factor analysis machine. *Understanding statistics: Statistical issues in psychology, education, and the social sciences*, 2(1), 13-43.
- Spanierman, L. B., Clark, D. A., & Kim, Y. (2021). Reviewing racial microaggressions research: Documenting targets' experiences, harmful sequelae, and resistance strategies. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 16(5), 1037-1059.
- Sue, D. W. (Ed.). (2010). *Microaggressions and marginality: Manifestation, dynamics, and impact*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Sue, D. W., & Spanierman, L. (2020). *Microaggressions in everyday life*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Torres, M. B., Salles, A., & Cochran, A. (2019). Recognizing and reacting to microaggressions in medicine and surgery. *JAMA surgery*, 154(9), 868-872.
- Torino, G. C., Rivera, D. P., Capodilupo, C. M., Nadal, K. L., & Sue, D. W. (2019). Microaggression theory: What the future holds. *Microaggression theory*, 309-328.
- Watson, B., Clarke, C., Swallow, V., & Forster, S. (2005). Exploratory factor analysis of the research and development culture index among qualified nurses. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 14(9), 1042-1047.
- Watson, R., & Thompson, D. R. (2006). Use of factor analysis in Journal of Advanced Nursing: literature review. *Journal of advanced nursing*, 55(3), 330-341.
- Westover, J. (2025). Managing microaggressions: Strategies for responding to subtle bias in the workplace. *Human Capital Leadership Review: Human Capital Innovations, LLC*, 17(2).
- Williams, M. T. (2020). Microaggressions: Clarification, evidence, and impact. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 15(1), 3-26.
- Williams, M. T., Skinta, M. D., & Martin-Willett, R. (2021). After Pierce and Sue: A revised racial microaggressions taxonomy. *Perspectives on psychological science*, 16(5), 991-1007.
- Yong, A. G., & Pearce, S. (2013). A beginner's guide to factor analysis: Focusing on exploratory factor analysis. *Tutorials in quantitative methods for psychology*, 9(2), 79-94.

